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1 TITLE

2 CAPTURING WASTE RECYCLING SCIENCE

3 KEYWORDS

4 Tech mining; Search strategies; Waste recycling; Bibliometric analysis

5 ABSTRACT

6 Many institutions from the public and private sector are interested in the characterization of
7 the research taking place in waste recycling (WR) science. Tech mining analysis can be applied
8 to scientific databases with this purpose in mind, but difficulties do arise when designing the
9 search strategy to effectively capture this multidisciplinary area. This paper introduces the
10 process followed to build a query system that aims to solve this problem. This system has been
11 applied to a selection of scientific databases, and the steps followed to download and clean
12 the data are detailed. Initial results are explained, indicating the relevance of each database
13 and quantifying the overlap among them. The main subjects behind the retrieved data have
14 been identified, namely, chemistry, biology and environmental sciences. A precision test
15 conducted by random sampling indicated that, with a confidence level of 95%, the proportion
16 of WR articles is between 74.2 and 79.2% of the retrieved items, while recall is expected to be
17 high according to available classifications. These results are deemed to be satisfactory enough
18 for basing forthcoming tech mining analyses on this query system.

19 1. INTRODUCTION

20 There are many institutions from the public and private sector interested in the
21 characterization and forecasting of the research taking place in waste recycling (WR) science.
22 This is a highly multidisciplinary field that comprises knowledge coming from various branches
23 of science, including social sciences [1]. In addition to this, the waste management industry is
24 formed by a wide range of activities including collection, transport, processing,
25 recycling/disposal and the monitoring of waste materials [2]. This variety of activities and
26 scientific research areas adds extra complexity to the decision making process within this field,
27 enhancing the need for timely and accurate information about what is going on in it.

28 Tech mining analysis can play a key role in the assessment of R&D policies in WR, providing
29 valuable information about the worldwide scientific research that is going on, the main actors
30 in the field and many other innovation-related indicators. Tech mining can be defined as the
31 application of text mining tools to science and technology information, informed by an
32 understanding of technological innovation processes [3]. Scientific publication databases are a
33 global and trustworthy source of information that can be effectively exploited via text mining
34 in order to extract information about research taking place in WR. The problem arises from the
35 very multidisciplinary nature of this science, which invariably calls for the building of an ad-hoc
36 search strategy to capture the nucleus of this science from the databases, and clearly define its
37 subfields. The aim of this paper is to provide an overview of the method followed to build a set
38 of queries oriented to capture the scientific production in WR, for the eleven year interval
39 2000-2010. The database choice, as well as the downloading and data cleaning processes are
40 described, and some initial results are reported. This work is previous to the elaboration of

41 other tech mining studies oriented to WR research activity, including social network studies
42 and the building of a WR map of science.

43 2. METHODOLOGY

44 2.1. PRECEDENTS

45 The starting point of this paper is the work done (in press) by Garechana et al. (2012), tracking
46 the cognitive changes experienced in WR science from the years 2005 to 2010, via tech mining
47 tools. The criteria then followed to retrieve the items published in WR research were derived
48 from the identification of the core journals in this science, and the Web of Science (WOS)
49 Subject Categories (SC) which were used to identify the underlying key cognitive areas.

50 A thorough study of the keywords found in the sample of Garechana et al. gave an overall
51 impression of the major research topics in this field; however, some doubts remained as to
52 what activities were to be included under the WR concept. These doubts led to the search of
53 formal definitions, mainly in governmental and official public agency websites. An overall
54 consensus was found, with some exceptions, about two facts of what can be considered WR:

- 55 a) It does not only involve the remanufacturing or reprocessing of materials so that they
56 can be used again, but also the collection, classification/separation of wastes and the
57 subsequent marketing of recycled products.
- 58 b) Recycling is not only about the reutilization of the spent materials in their original
59 form. A discarded rubber tire might be reused as an industrial resource not in the form
60 of recycled rubber, but in form of fuel for a cement kiln.

61 Some sources explicitly exclude the thermal combustion of wastes from the umbrella of WR
62 [4], and obviously it would be as such in the case of mere incineration without energy
63 recovery. However, the studies conducted by Garechana et al. (2012) and consulted experts
64 point out that the Waste-to-Energy concept is an important area in waste management. Direct
65 combustion methods are the least desirable option to recover energy from waste, and are
66 subject to strict regulations [5] but other procedures aimed at obtaining fuel from waste are
67 increasingly important. Taking these facts into account, the authors opted to choose the
68 following inclusive definition of WR:

69 “A method of recovering wastes as resources which includes the collection, and often involving
70 the treatment, of waste products for use as a replacement of all or part of the raw material in
71 a manufacturing process.” [6]

72 This definition is broad enough to include the recovery of many inputs like water or energy
73 while considering the recycling process as a whole, including collection, characterization and
74 classification of waste. Other available definitions are considerably broader but somehow ill
75 defined: “Reusing materials and objects in original or changed forms rather than discarding
76 them as waste” [6] while others put the energy recovery from waste under the definition of
77 waste recovery, eluding the word “recycling” [7].

78 2.2. THE QUERY SYSTEM

79 The work conducted by Porter et al [8] to build a set of queries that define the boundaries of
80 the science of nanotechnology has been a source of inspiration and methodology for this
81 paper, as well as the process detailed in the work of Kostoff [9] to retrieve the literature
82 corresponding to a particular area. The authors opted for a Boolean search term approach,
83 given the fact that temporal and financial limitations of this study discouraged the alternative
84 approach referred to as “bootstrapping” by Porter et al [8], and considering on the other hand
85 the advantages of modularity and flexibility derived from the Boolean approach.

86 2.2.1.COMPILED OF TERMS

87 An exploratory set of queries, based on the previously mentioned keyword study, was run on
88 SCI and SSCI, and the results analyzed. The overview of WR activities and different types of
89 waste sources given by Demirbas [2] was also a good starting point to define the subfields
90 within WR. The items retrieved in this first attempt were examined by taking samples and
91 reading the available fields, especially title and abstract, to determine if the results fitted in the
92 aforementioned WR definition. This process proved to be extremely effective to discover
93 various synonyms and acronyms of WR related terms, as well as to identify some non-desired
94 meanings of the initial keywords. Important words in WR science were identified thanks to the
95 reading of literally hundreds of titles and abstracts, and their suitability considered for
96 including them in the queries. The correct interpretation of the retrieved items was
97 considerably eased by the qualifications of the authors of this paper, the main author holding a
98 university degree in chemical engineering and the second main author a master’s degree in
99 environmental sciences. The analysis was further complemented by checking the glossary
100 service of the European Environmental Agency [6] and US Environmental Protection Agency
101 [10]. These two websites were intensively used as vocabulary source and qualified information
102 point; both were selected due to their trustworthiness and the richness of their terminology
103 services.

104 2.2.2.ADJUSTING RETRIEVED ITEMS TO WR

105 At this point, the researchers had collected a fairly lengthy set of keywords from various
106 branches of WR, but when testing them via simple queries in various databases, the following
107 problems arose:

- 108 - Some queries introduced significant noise in the sample, for example, retrieving
109 publications about mere disposal or incineration of waste, did not deal with the
110 aforementioned WR definition. A clear case can be found when retrieving publications
111 about landfilling. Landfills produce various gases that can be used as an energy source
112 [11], however, mere landfilling cannot be considered as WR, according to the chosen
113 definition.
- 114 - Other important keywords have a too broad a meaning. The term biomass is an
115 example; this term refers to any biological matter, from a population of animal or
116 vegetal organisms (fish biomass) to crops specifically grown for obtaining biofuel. It is
117 necessary to modify the query to obtain publications oriented to extract energy from
118 waste biomass resources.
- 119 - The same acronym can refer to very dissimilar things. Acronyms should be included in
120 the queries after carefully evaluating the retrieved items.

121 The solution proposed by the authors was to develop some co-occurrence modules, to restrict
122 the retrieval of the queries to the boundaries of WR. The choice of the proper module to co-
123 occur with each keyword was made by trial and error, looking for at least roughly 70% of
124 retrieved items directly related with WR. Modules are listed below:

- 125 - WASTE MODULE: (SCRAP* OR LITTER* OR GARBAGE* OR LEFTOVER* OR TRASH* OR
126 RESIDUE* OR WAST* OR DEBRIS*).
- 127 - RECYCLE MODULE: (TREAT* OR RECYCL* OR RECOV* OR REUT* OR REUS*).
- 128 - ENERGY MODULE: (ENERG* OR FUEL*).

129 The keywords were usually searched in “title” field, aiming to introduce the minimum noise in
130 the sample, but good results were obtained when unmistakably WR-related terms were
131 searched in “all fields”. Co-occurrence with modules was applied in “all fields”, when necessary
132 (see Table 1). Some technical terms corresponding to specific chemical, metallurgical or
133 biological treatments were detected in WR, but in many cases they had other applications
134 apart from WR activities and introduced appreciable noise in the sample. The authors decided
135 not to include them for two additional reasons: first, they added very few items that had not
136 already been captured by the query system, and second, a low number of queries considerably
137 eased the running of the set in multiple databases. The corrective effect exerted upon the
138 ambiguous terms by the system of co-occurrence modules was deemed to be satisfactory,
139 after analyzing some random samples of those retrieved in WOS databases.

140 2.2.3. FINAL STRUCTURE AND EXPERT ASSESSMENT

141 The final structure of the query system is shown in the Venn diagram (Figure 1).

142

143

144 **Figure 1 Venn diagram showing the structure of the query system. The size does not exactly**
145 **reflect the records retrieved by each node.**

146 Each number in the diagram corresponds to a query as shown in Table 1. A great deal of
 147 scientific production regarding WR (60%) is captured by query 1 (central node), being
 148 surprisingly accurate, given the broad terms used. The nodes named “Industry specific and
 149 general vocabulary” and “Land and substratum recovery” both retrieve roughly 12% of items
 150 while “Waste-to-energy” node retrieves 10%. In spite of being a very important area of WR,
 151 the specific “Water Recovery” queries only retrieve 6% of items, this is due to the term
 152 “wastewater”, the main keyword in water recovery activities, which gets captured by query 1
 153 via the truncation of term “wast*”. The percentages given here are orientative data obtained
 154 when running this query set in SCI and SSCI databases for year 2010.

155 The final set is listed in Table1, containing 30 queries plus 2 exclusion queries according to
 156 WOS syntax, where field tag TI refers to field “Title”, and TS refers to “All fields” (title, abstract
 157 and keywords). An optional query is given to be run on “Keyword” field, where available. This
 158 query has not been used in this work, given the fact that not all search engines under study
 159 allowed running a query restricted to “Keyword” field, and the comparative across databases
 160 required the query system to be homogeneous.

161 Exclusion queries were introduced in this system to avoid capturing not WR-related items. An
 162 important step in the building of exclusion queries is the detection of “toxic terms” by carefully
 163 examining the vocabulary suggested by the database search engine when running the
 164 searches, this service was originally intended to help finding related items, but it proved to be
 165 very useful for us to detect unwanted terms. This step can also be conducted by downloading
 166 the retrieved items and importing them to text mining software Vantage Point¹ for keyword
 167 analysis, this software offers many different options in this sense. The very laborious task of
 168 testing the different variations of queries against databases provides the analyst not only with
 169 many synonyms and new words to try, but also with the identification of “toxic terms” that, if
 170 properly identified, can be included in an exclusion query to increase the precision of the
 171 system. Roughly 4% of the retrieved items were identified as noise by these two exclusion
 172 queries, and they were excluded prior to information downloading phase. Please note that
 173 queries may have to be adapted to the syntax of each database.

Query Number	Query
EXCLUSION QUERIES:	
TI=("time wast*" OR "wasted time*" OR "waste of time*" OR "wast* time" OR "heat wast*" OR "wasted heat*")	
TS=("product life cycl*" OR "radioactive wast*" OR "nuclear wast*" OR endosom*)	
OPTIONAL QUERY²	
KEYWORD=recycle*	
WASTE-TO-ENERGY	
30	TS=((biomass AND (ENERGY MODULE) OR bioethan* OR biogas* OR biofuel* OR "energy recov*") AND (WASTE MODULE)) NOT TI=(wast* OR recycl*)
29	TS=("waste to energy" AND "energy to wast*") NOT TI=(wast* OR recycl*)

¹ See <http://www.thevantagepoint.com/>.

² To be included when the database under study allows running queries restricted to keyword field.

28	TI=((SRF OR "solid refuse fuel*" OR "solid recovered fuel*" OR RDF OR "refuse derived fuel*") NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=ENERGY MODULE
27	TI=(methana* OR methani* OR methane* NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(WASTE MODULE)
26	TI=(incinerat* NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(ENERGY MODULE OR RECYCLE MODULE)
25	TI=(landfill* NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(ENERGY MODULE)
PAPER INDUSTRY	
24	TS=("black liquor*" AND gasificat*) NOT TI=(wast* OR recycl*)
23	TI=("mill sludge*" OR deink* NOT (wast* OR recycl*))
VARIOUS INDUSTRIES	
22	TS=("product reu*" OR "reverse logistic*" OR "reverse suppl*" OR "closed loop suppl*" OR remanufact*)
21	TS=("construction and demolit*") NOT TI=(wast* OR recycl*)
20	TI=("automotive shredder residue*" NOT (wast* OR recycl*))
19	TI=("cement kiln" NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(WASTE MODULE)
18	TI=(cullet* NOT (wast* OR recycl*))
17	TI=(depolymer* NOT (depolymerase OR wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(WASTE MODULE)
AGRICULTURAL RESIDUES	
16	TI=("cereal straw*" OR "corn stover*" OR "rice husk*" OR "agricultural resid*" OR manure* NOT (wast* OR recycl*))
ELECTRIC/ELECTRONICAL RESIDUES	
15	TI=("printed circuit board*" NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(RECYCLE MODULE)
14	TS=WEEE* NOT TI=(wast* OR recycl*)
LAND AND SUBSTRATUM RECOVERY	
13	TS=(bioremediat*) NOT TI=(wast* OR recycl*)
12	TI=(biochar* OR "terra preta" OR charcoal* NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(WASTE MODULE)
11	TI=((compost* OR vermicompost* OR brownfield* OR biosolid*) NOT (wast* OR recycl*))
WATER RECOVERY	
10	TI=(effluent* NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(RECYCLE MODULE)
9	TI=((denitrif* AND water*) OR "reject water*" OR (sewage AND sludge) NOT (wast* OR recycl*))

GENERAL VOCABULARY	
8	TI=(anaerob* OR aerob*) AND TS=(WASTE MODULE) NOT TI=(wast* OR recycl*)
7	TI=(feedstock* NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(WASTE MODULE)
6	TI=((scrap* OR leftover*) NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(RECYCLE MODULE)
5	TI=(gasific* NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(WASTE MODULE)
4	TS=(postconsumer* OR post-consumer* NOT (wast* OR recycl*))
3	TI=("fly ash*" OR "bottom ash*" NOT (wast* OR recycl*)) AND TS=(RECYCLE MODULE)
2	TI=("mechanical biological treat*" NOT (wast* OR recycl*))
WASTE RECYCLING	
1	TI=(wast* OR recycl*) OR TS=((wast* AND recycl*) OR (recycl* near/5 (scrap* OR garbage* OR leftover* OR trash* OR residue* OR debris*)))

174 **Table 1 Set of queries, the syntax is that of WOS databases. Queries adapted for other**
175 **databases are available upon request.**

176 A pilot set of queries and the Venn diagram were shown to experts working in metallurgic, e-
177 waste and waste oil recycling sectors, who endorsed the overall approach, showing interest in
178 future tech mining analysis carried out in WR field. Expertise from academic colleagues at the
179 University of the Basque Country has been obtained from the early stages of this study, in
180 areas like wastewater treatment or biology. In some cases, experts recommended candidate
181 terms to be included in the set, mainly referring to particular technologies they applied in their
182 respective industries or research, and these terms were tested against the scientific databases
183 prior to their inclusion in the set. Some problems encountered when working with very
184 specific, technical words have been explained in section 2.2.2. It was also found that the
185 contributions of actors in WR industries were limited to their particular activity or technology,
186 and in spite of being valuable opinions, the authors found it necessary to look for the feedback
187 of decision makers in a wider scope, given the breadth of the field object of study

188 A meeting with IHOBE was arranged to obtain this prime endorsement. IHOBE is the public
189 corporation in charge of supporting the Basque Government's Department for the
190 Environment, Spatial Planning, Agriculture and Fisheries, in the development of its
191 environmental policy [12]. Project documentation was made available prior to the meeting
192 and feedback was asked for concerning methodology followed and the activity areas
193 considered in WR. The answer given by the managers of IHOBE was positive, suggesting minor
194 modifications that were subsequently implemented, and showing great interest in future tech
195 mining analysis based on this search strategy. The WR map of science, currently in process,
196 raised special interest because of its possibilities to support environmental decision making.

197 2.3. THE DATABASES

198 The aim of this study is to capture the research literature corresponding to WR research, so
199 scientific publication databases are the target of our query set. The possibility of merging the
200 results of several databases using Vantage Point made it possible for the authors to look for
201 the maximum amount of information, but other factors had to be considered: On the one
202 hand, the broadest possible coverage of scientific databases is desirable to capture the
203 maximum scientific activity taking place, whereas on the other, there are computational limits
204 for processing such amounts of information and database subscriptions are limited by
205 available financial resources.

206 The final goal is to have a sufficiently large amount of items to support any kind of tech mining
207 analysis. Further studies may require the adaptation of this query system to patent databases
208 with the purpose of capturing the technological landscape of WR, but this is beyond the scope
209 of this paper.

210 The criteria followed to choose the databases were based on the amount of information they
211 contained and its availability. Together with pure scientific databases, social-sciences oriented
212 databases were also to be included, taking into account the role they play in WR field [1]. An
213 initial guide for choosing the best databases in WR science was found in the University of
214 Connecticut database locator [13], and their proposal for environmental sciences databases
215 was analyzed by the authors.

216 Two WOS databases were included, namely SCI and SSCI, looking for its broad coverage of
217 several scientific disciplines and the availability of full citation data. The ease of its
218 downloading process makes this database a very suitable one for tech mining purposes.
219 SCOPUS was judged as an adequate complement to WOS databases, due to the large amount
220 of information available, not only in the form of scientific or congress publications but also
221 trade journals whose information the authors consider interesting for further analysis. This
222 database only allows 2,000 results of any query to be checked, so the downloading process
223 had to be adapted to retrieve a maximum of 2,000 items in each step, which caused a
224 multiplication in the number of queries and a marked increase in the workload. Additionally,
225 we were interested in including INSPEC in the database set with the purpose of introducing
226 extra technical information, given its specialization in sciences and engineering. This database
227 limits checking to 4,000 results, so queries had to be adapted as previously explained.

228 EBSCO Green file was included to further complement the dataset in environmental aspect.
229 This is a multidisciplinary database specialized in research about the human impact to the
230 environment, including recycling issues [14].

231 Vantage Point software was used to create sub-datasets for particular analysis, as well as for
232 merging the items retrieved from the different databases, subsequently eliminating the strong
233 existing duplicities, as databases do considerably overlap in their coverage. Computational
234 resources were insufficient to accomplish this task in a single step, so merging was done taking
235 biannual intervals and limiting the fields only to those that were essential for the analysis
236 taking place. The expression "WR database" is going to be used from this point onward to refer
237 to the global database obtained with this work.

238 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

239 3.1. ITEMS AND SUBJECTS ACROSS DATABASES

240 Some characterization studies have been conducted on the downloaded WR database. For
241 normalization purposes, only peer reviewed journal articles have been considered. Figure 2
242 shows the amount of articles retrieved by the query system from each considered database,
243 after eliminating duplicities. SCOPUS is leading the set, probably due to its wider coverage of
244 peer-reviewed publications: 18,500 in July 2011 [16] vs. 11,471 publications covered by SCI +
245 SSCI, as indicated in their master journal list [17]. Both INSPEC and Green File show a similar
246 number of items. The overall trend shows an increasing number of publications over time for
247 all databases, excepting Green File.

248

249

250 **Figure 2. Articles retrieved in peer reviewed journals, from year 2000 to 2010**

251 It should also be noted that a significant overlap exists among these four databases, estimated
252 at roughly 38% for journal articles; this is clearly appreciated in the “TOTAL” curve in Figure 2.
253 After eliminating the duplicities, a total of 102,301 journal articles have been captured in the
254 indicated databases for the yearly interval 2000-2010.

255 Some of the studied databases add extra information by adding a “subject” or “classification”
256 field to locate each item in a particular area of knowledge. These categories can be used to
257 characterize the cognitive framework of the retrieved WR database: WOS subject categories
258 have been widely used to characterize scientific fields [18] or even as a cognitive unit to build a
259 global map of science [19]. Subject areas in SCOPUS have also been used for research
260 characterization [20]. Table 2 contains the top 10 subjects as retrieved in WOS and SCOPUS
261 with this query system. The authors considered it interesting to add a third column with
262 INSPEC classification code. The exact contents of each subject category may differ between
263 databases, but the authors consider that a good overall picture of the areas behind the WR
264 database can be appreciated from the contents of Table 2.

265

WOS (SUBJECT CATEGORY)	SCOPUS (SUBJECT AREA)	INSPEC (CLASSIFICATION CODE)
Environmental Sciences (17.3%)	Environmental Science (25.2%)	E0230 Environmental Issues (16.5%)
Engineering, Environmental (10.9%)	Chemical Engineering (11.4%)	E1840 Recycling (11.8%)
Engineering, Chemical (6.9%)	Agricultural and Biological Sciences (10.3%)	E1525 Industrial Processes (10.4%)
Biotechnology & Applied Microbiology (6.6%)	Chemistry (7.8%)	E1710 Engineering Materials (7.1%)
Water Resources (5.9%)	Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology (7.0%)	E3628 Biotechnology Industry (2.4%)
Energy & Fuels (4.4%)	Engineering (7.0%)	E1780 Products and Commodities (2.3%)
Agricultural Engineering (2.6%)	Immunology and Microbiology (5.9%)	E3624 Fuel Processing Industry (1.7%)
Engineering, Civil (2.4%)	Materials Science (5.7%)	E3030 Construction Industry (1.6%)
Soil Science (2.3%)	Earth and Planetary Sciences (5.2%)	A3636 Metallurgical Industries (1.5%)
Chemistry, Multidisciplinary (2.3%)	Energy (3.7%)	E3626 Chemical Industry (1.5%)

266 **Table 2 Subject characterization of WR database, the %share of each category is indicated in**
267 **brackets.**

268 Environmental sciences dominate the items from WOS, SCOPUS and INSPEC, followed by
269 chemistry (including chemical engineering) and biology (considering a group formed by
270 biotechnology, microbiology and biochemistry subjects). Energy and agricultural sciences also
271 have their marked share of importance. INSPEC categories show a fairly different structure if
272 compared with SCOPUS and WOS, this is partly due to the higher disaggregation level available
273 in this field and the specialization of this database in engineering issues, but no strong
274 discordances are observed. We could say that Table 2 points out the scientific areas a WR
275 researcher or decision maker should pay attention to, especially when dealing with this field in
276 the broad sense, aligned with the scope of this paper. Narrower scopes, whether it is focused
277 on a particular technology or a particular type of waste, would require an ad hoc analysis far
278 from the aims of this paper.

279 3.2. PRECISION AND RECALL

280 An analysis about the precision and recall of this query system has been conducted upon the
281 data retrieved from WOS (61,635 journal articles), according to the definition cited in section
282 2.1.

283 The precision will be determined by analyzing a sample of journal articles to calculate the
284 proportion of noise in the sample, that is to say, items not directly related with WR science
285 that have been unwittingly captured. A confidence level of 95 % and a margin of error of 5%
286 have been pragmatically established to determine the size of the sample to be taken. The
287 initial proportion of articles meeting the definition has been conservatively estimated at 50%,
288 thus maximizing the size of the sample. This led to the random selection of 382 journal articles

289 to be part of the sample. The title and abstract of every item in this sample were carefully read
290 and analyzed by the authors to decide whether a particular item should be considered WR or
291 not, using web glossaries {{343 European Environment Agency 2011; 344 US EPA 2012}} and
292 other web resources to clear up the meaning of some specialized terms. The full paper was
293 read when doubts raised, and academic colleagues from the University of the Basque Country
294 were consulted when needed. This process was considerably eased by the qualification of the
295 main authors (Section 2.2.1) and the typical redaction of a WR paper, given the fact that these
296 papers usually clearly state their purpose of studying the recycling/recovering of some kind of
297 material or energy. 293 papers were found to meet the definition, so we are 95% confident
298 that the proportion of WR articles present in the database lies between 74.2 and 79.2%. This is
299 a proportion deemed adequate by similar studies in the field of nanotechnology [8] that have
300 been successfully used to conduct tech mining studies [18].

301 The recall will quantify the number of truly relevant records about WR science that we are
302 missing. This is somewhat complex, since it implies the prior determination of the total
303 universe of WR publications, or at least, the essential core of WR science that should be
304 captured by this strategy. In a large, highly multidisciplinary field like WR, with its fuzzy
305 boundaries, this is a fairly difficult issue to deal with and, in fact, this paper would not be
306 necessary in case some definitive criteria were available to detect the whole research taking
307 place around WR. The many existing definitions of WR (see section 2.1) add extra complexity
308 to this task, making it difficult to find any subject categorization or other type of publicly
309 available cognitive unit that fits on the WR definition chosen for this work. The option of
310 selecting a set of key journals and considering them the vessel of WR knowledge was
311 considered, but there are many underlying problems regarding to this option, such as
312 determining the degree of alignment of journals with the aforementioned WR definition, as
313 well as deciding the type of journals (academic journals, trade journals, JCR indexed or not...)
314 to be considered. The issue of defining the WR research universe by taking a set of journals is a
315 subject of research by itself.

316 Another option, widely used with research characterization purposes, consists of using the
317 classification codes available in databases as cognitive categories that bring together the
318 knowledge pertaining to a certain discipline. The accuracy of these classification codes has
319 been put into question by some papers, but successful works have been conducted using them
320 as analytical unit, as explained in section 3.1. INSPEC database offers an interesting
321 classification scheme containing a specific category for recycling research (E1840) that can be
322 easily compared with the items retrieved by this query system by looking into the search field
323 "Classification Code". Although far from being the definitive criteria, the authors believe that
324 E1840 code could be used for giving a ballpark figure of the recall of this query system, taking
325 into account the following shortcomings: First, the contents of this category are conditioned to
326 the recall of the database itself, and second, our inclusive definition of WR is considerably
327 wider than the scope of E1840 category. Despite this, capturing a significant part of the items
328 under this category would be a plus for our approach. The recall test was conducted restricting
329 the items to journal articles written in English, and using the optional query considered for
330 databases allowing the search field "Keyword" (see section 2.2.3). The query system captured
331 97% of the items under the E1840 category, predicting a high recall rate for this retrieval
332 strategy.

333 4. CONCLUSIONS

334 “Waste recycling” is a concept comprising of a wide range of activities, including collection,
335 classification/separation of wastes and the subsequent marketing of recycled products. The
336 wide range of recyclable waste materials and recycling processes make this a profoundly
337 interdisciplinary field.

338 A set of 30 queries complemented by two exclusion queries has been built with the aim of
339 capturing the scientific production in this field. The methodology followed combines the areas
340 and keywords detected by previous works [1] as well as keywords coming from qualified
341 glossary services. A trial and error fine-tuning of the terms to be included in each query has
342 been conducted, assisted by expert assessment in the more complex issues. This process
343 proved to be a very effective method to delve deeper into the jargon of WR. An approach of
344 co-occurrence modules has been adopted to avoid capturing articles beyond the target. The
345 overall approach has been reviewed with IHOBE, a public corporation in charge of supporting
346 government decision makers when developing the environmental policies of the Basque
347 Country, obtaining positive feedback from them.

348 This query system has been run on four databases that were chosen either according to their
349 coverage of worldwide scientific production (WOS, SCOPUS) or their specialization in
350 environmental sciences and engineering (Green File, INSPEC). 102,301 journal articles were
351 retrieved in this process for the yearly interval 2000-2010, and the overlap among the
352 databases has been quantified (roughly 38%), meaning that almost 4 journal articles out of 10
353 are present in more than one database. Subject classifications have been analyzed where
354 available, and the more relevant sciences behind WR have been identified, in broad terms they
355 would be: environmental sciences, chemical sciences and biological sciences. Agricultural and
356 energy studies also show a significant share of importance.

357 Finally, a random sample of articles has been analyzed to test the accuracy of the query
358 system; the results indicate a proportion of 74.2-79.2% of WR articles with a confidence level
359 of 95%, therefore validating the precision of the followed methodology. Some tech mining
360 studies are currently being carried out using this WR database, the main goal being the
361 building of a WR science map, a project which IHOBE has already expressed interest and with
362 whom we expect to continue working, supporting our analysis with an expert-opinion source
363 directly related with decision making in the field object of study.

364 5. LESSONS LEARNED

365 This section is a compilation of facts and suggestions that may help tech miners to capture the
366 research taking place around other complex, may be ill-defined, large research areas with
367 fuzzy boundaries like WR. Please feel free to contact with the corresponding author in case any
368 additional information is needed.

369 This study considered interesting to design a query system that could be run with minimum
370 variation on multiple databases, looking for enlarging as much as possible the amount of
371 information retrieved. This is a troublesome sort of thing to do, and the following facts should
372 be taken into account:

373 - Databases often differ in the syntax of queries, and “help” section of the search engine
374 should be carefully read before anything, especially when dealing with truncated
375 terms and the like. Boolean operators and proximity operators can also be different
376 across databases, and search fields may also differ in their description. These facts are
377 usually well explained in “help” section.

378 - The bias of some databases towards a particular branch of science strongly determines
379 the precision of some terms, a high-precision query in INSPEC may be undesirable for
380 running in WOS. The proper use of co-occurrence modules usually helped to avoid
381 this problem, but attention must be pay to the behavior of specialized databases.

382 “Toxic terms” to be included in exclusion queries can be detected by paying attention to the
383 vocabulary suggested by the database search engine when running the searches. A similar
384 analysis can be conducted importing the retrieved items to Vantage Point and analyzing the
385 main keywords present in sample. This has been explained in section 2.2.3.

386 Many databases limit the number of items that can be viewed or downloaded to a few
387 thousands. This limitation can be successfully avoided by dividing the query in time intervals
388 that meet the limit and subsequently merging the slices using Vantage Point.

389 The process of validating a query is labor-intensive and can be quite boring, but it is a really
390 good source of synonyms and extra terms to include in the strategy, as well as to detect “toxic
391 terms”. The analyst should be sure of exhausting this method, which must be adequately
392 complemented with expert assessment.

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